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CONTENTS

BUDGETING BASED ON THE BALANCED SCORECARD SYSTEM IN STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING.....	8
Pardaeva Shakhnoza Abdinabievna	
TURIZM SOHASIDA TARJIMA NAZARIYASINING O'RNI.....	13
Bahronova Charos Mirabbos qizi	
THE ROLE OF ESG PRINCIPLES AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CORPORATE SOCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS.....	16
Shokhrukh Abdusalimovich Muratkosimov	
A COMPARATIVE SEMANTIC FIELD ANALYSIS OF "BENEFIT" ACROSS ENGLISH AND UZBEK CULTURES.....	23
Mohira Husanovna Divanova	
ROSSIYA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA DEPOZIT OPERATSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI.....	30
Rahimov Akmal Matyaqubovich	
USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES AGAINST CYBER THREATS IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR.....	37
Nuratdinov Xushnid Begzadovich, Erejepov Kewlimjay Kaymatdinovich	
PUL-KREDIT SIYOSATI INSTRUMENTLARIDAN FOYDALANISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH..	42
A.A. Ismailov	
"O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI" AJNING AMALIY IQTISODIY HOLATI TAHLILI VA OPSIONLARNI ANIQLASH.....	48
Bobojonova Zarnigor Shokirovna	
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHMS FOR AUTOMATED SKIN DISEASE DIAGNOSIS FROM DERMOSCOPIC IMAGES.....	56
Nazirova Elmira Shodmonovna, Abdusalomova Shokhista Boboyor qizi	
STRATEGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FINANCIAL MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL AND GREEN TRANSFORMATION.....	61
Muftaydinov Mansur Kiyomidinovich	
TOURISM POTENTIAL OF UZBEKISTAN AND FINANCIAL FACTORS FOR ITS DEVELOPMENT.....	68
Bau Long	
CASH FLOWS OF "TERRITORIAL ELECTRIC NETWORKS" JSC: COMPREHENSIVE ACCOUNTING ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO IMPROVEMENT.....	75
Djuraev Davlat Djonibekovich	
MONETARY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	78
A.A. Ismailov	
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SERVICE SECTOR OF REGIONS.....	83
Abdikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	
KNOWLEDGE STRATEGY AND ITS SYSTEM OF INDICATORS IN STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING.....	89
Pardaeva Shakhnoza Abdinabievna, Pardaeva Zulfizar Alimovna	
ANALYSIS OF THE REGIONAL DYNAMICS AND STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LABOR MIGRATION.....	95
Mukhtorbek Rahimboyev, Alibek Normurodov	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA KREDIT RISKLARNI BAHOLOVCHI TIZIMLARNI ISHLAB CHIQISH. MIJOZ SCORE MODEL VA QARORLARNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	104
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN ESG IMPLEMENTATION: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.....	111
Khusenova Mekhrangiz	

FORMATION OF MEDICAL TOURISM CLUSTERS IN THE REGION	115
Yusupova Mehribon O'ktamovna	
DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE INTEGRATION OF SCADA AND ERP SYSTEMS IN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	120
Abdullaev Munis Kurbonovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN IMPLEMENTING GREEN PUBLIC PROCUREMENT AND LESSONS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	125
Ruzimurodova Charos Ural qizi	
AGROTECHNICAL AND INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING GRAIN PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY	129
Turayeva Gulizahro	
MINERALOGICAL OCCURRENCE OF RARE METALS IN THE INGICHKA DEPOSIT AND DEVELOPMENT OF TUNGSTEN EXTRACTION TECHNOLOGY	133
Shodiyev Abbos, Dononov Jasur, Safarov Gulomjon	
STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP COOPERATION IN THE GREEN ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN	140
Zukhra Bakhramovna Abdikarimova	
TIME MANAGEMENT IN THE CRAFT ECONOMY: STRATEGIES FOR OPTIMIZING THE TIME RESOURCES OF INDIVIDUAL PRODUCERS	148
Feruza Nazrillaevna Israilova	
DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL SUSTAINABILITY GOALS	154
Muminova Mokhchekhra	
FEATURES AND FACTORS OF WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	160
Ibodullayeva Malohat Sirojiddin qizi	
MECHANISMS FOR POVERTY REDUCTION THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE SERVICE SECTOR.....	165
Dauletmuratov Adilbay Mirzabaevich	
IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF ENVIRONMENTAL AUDITING AT ENTERPRISES BASED ON A RISK-ORIENTED APPROACH AND DIGITAL EVIDENCE	171
Abdullayev Khurshidjon Nazrullo o'g'li, Khurshidjon Abdullayev	
INTEGRATION MECHANISMS OF DIGITAL ECONOMY TECHNOLOGIES INTO REGIONAL GOVERNANCE SYSTEMS	176
Kurbonova Malika Ahmad kizi	
DEVELOPMENT OF A LOGICAL-LINGUISTIC MODEL OF THE KOREAN NOUN CATEGORY AND CREATION OF A PREFIX AND AFFIX DATABASE.....	181
Yendirboyeva Zumrad Zohidjon qizi	
THEORETICAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF MANAGING STATE SHARES IN BUSINESS ENTITIES	186
Akmaljon Valijonov	
ENSURING OBJECT SECURITY AND ANALYZING INFORMATION SECURITY BASED ON NEURAL NETWORKS.....	190
Babayazov Saidbek Po'latovich, Sultamuratova Dilnoza Gulmuratovna	
FUNDAMENTAL METHODS FOR IDENTIFYING AI-GENERATED DATA IN ACADEMIC AND ONLINE PUBLICATIONS USING MACHINE LEARNING AND NLP MODELS.....	196
Abdullaev Munis Kurbonovich, Kungratov Ilmurod Kuzibay ugli	
QUALITY ASSURANCE OF NON-AUTOCLAVED AERATED CONCRETE WITH THE ADDITION OF CMC (CARBOXYMETHYL CELLULOSE)	204
Pulatova D.G., Akhundjanov K.A.	
INTEGRATION MECHANISMS OF DIGITAL ECONOMY TECHNOLOGIES INTO REGIONAL GOVERNANCE SYSTEMS.....	210
Kurbonova Malika Ahmad kizi	

IMPROVING TAX ADMINISTRATION IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS SOLUTIONS	215
Shamsiyev O'ktam Sayfitdinovich	
ASSESSING THE SOURCES AND QUALITY OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH USING THE SOLOW MODEL.....	222
Turaev Bakhtiyor Ergashevich	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF BANKING SYSTEM DIGITALIZATION	228
Suyunov Feruz, Ergashov Firdavs, Norqulov Habibullo	
HARDWARE-AWARE PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION OF YOLOV8 FOR REAL-TIME APPLICATIONS: GPU ACCELERATION WITH TENSORRT AND AN ANALYTICAL FPGA COMPARISON.....	232
Ulugbek Tursunaliyev, Bakhromjon Tulkinov	
DEVELOPMENT OF SPATIAL INFORMATION MODELS OF TERRITORIAL DEVELOPMENT TAKING INTO ACCOUNT ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN AND THE ARAL REGION)	241
Reymova Gulmira Polatovna	
LEADERSHIP STYLES AND QUALITY ASSURANCE CULTURE IN UNIVERSITIES.....	248
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
SOCIO-ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH AND INCENTIVE SYSTEMS IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR.....	256
Zafar Ibragimovich Xakimov	
SOCIOLINGUISTIC FEATURES OF NEGATIVE AESTHETIC EVALUATION UNITS DENOTING PHYSICAL APPEARANCE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK.....	260
Qalandarova Shaxzoda Qurbonboy qizi	
REMITTANCE INFLOWS AND THE SUSTAINABILITY OF ECONOMIC GROWTH: A TIME-SERIES ANALYSIS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	265
O. B. Gimranova	
FORECAST INDICATORS, PROSPECTS, AND OUTCOMES OF DEVELOPING THE MECHANICAL ENGINEERING INDUSTRY THROUGH GREEN INVESTMENTS.....	271
Xursandov Komiljon Maxmatkulovich	
FEATURES AND FACTORS OF WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	276
Ibodullayeva Malohat Sirojiddin qizi	
FACTORS INFLUENCING TAX REVENUE EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	282
Jurayev Xusan Atamuratovich	
THE DIGITAL GASTRONOME: HOW TECHNOLOGY CONNECTS TOURISTS, RESTAURANTS, AND DIGITAL PLATFORMS	286
Freshta Qayoumi	
THE REPRESENTATION OF RESTRICTED LEXICON IN FRENCH LITERARY WORKS	290
Gulnoz Akhmedova	
RESEARCH ON THE TRANSMISSION MECHANISMS AND IMPLEMENTATION PATHS OF SHANDONG PROVINCE'S "SILVER ECONOMY" DEVELOPMENT EXPERIENCE IN THE FERGANA REGION	294
Zhang Zhe	
APPLICATION OF NET PRESENT VALUE ANALYSIS TO SHORT-TERM PERSONAL FINANCIAL DECISIONS	299
Akhunova Elena Anvarovna	
ECONOMIC OPPORTUNITIES FOR INCREASING EMPLOYMENT THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES IN KHOREZM REGION	307
Azadova Gulnoza Sardorbekovna	
DEVELOPMENT TRENDS AND INSTITUTIONAL FEATURES OF THE STOCK MARKET IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	313
Nargiza E. Jiyanova, Diana D. Qurbaniyazova	
MODELING AND FORECASTING THE SCIENTIFIC PUBLISHING ACTIVITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (A CASE STUDY OF SCOPUS DATA).....	321
Ozoda B. Sakieva	

MODELING AND FORECASTING THE SCIENTIFIC PUBLISHING ACTIVITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (A CASE STUDY OF SCOPUS DATA)

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ABSTRACT. The key factors influencing the international ranking indicators of higher education institutions are examined, with particular attention given to the dynamics of scientific publications indexed in the Scopus international scientific database. The research focuses on the scientific activities of the academic staff of Termiz State University and their participation in international publications during 2019–2025. Based on time-series analysis, exponential and polynomial trend models were developed to forecast the growth rate of scientific publications. The obtained results enabled the evaluation and interpretation of model parameters, providing a basis for relevant scientific conclusions.

Keywords: ordinary least squares method, Scopus international scientific database, exponential trend model, linear regression, regression model, model accuracy, forecast value, mean squared error.

ANNOTATSIYA. Oliy ta'lim muassasalarining xalqaro reyting ko'rsatkichlariga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillar, xususan, Scopus xalqaro ilmiy ma'lumotlar bazasidagi ilmiy nashrlar dinamikasi tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot obyekti sifatida Termiz davlat universiteti professor-o'qituvchilarining 2019–2025-yillardagi ilmiy faoliyati hamda ularning xalqaro nashrlardagi ishtiroki o'rganilgan. Vaqt qatorlari tahlili asosida ilmiy maqolalar sonining o'sish sur'atlarini prognozlash uchun eksponensial va polinomial trend modellari ishlab chiqilgan. Olingan natijalar asosida model parametrlarining baholanishi va tahlili amalga oshirilib, tegishli ilmiy xulosalar shakllantirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: eng kichik kvadratlar usuli, Scopus xalqaro ilmiy ma'lumotlar bazasi, eksponensial trend modeli, chiziqli regressiya, regressiya modeli, model aniqligi, prognoz qiymati, o'rtacha kvadratik xatolik.

АННОТАЦИЯ. Рассмотрены основные факторы, влияющие на показатели международных рейтингов высших учебных заведений, с акцентом на динамику научных публикаций, индексируемых в международной научной базе данных Scopus. В качестве объекта исследования выбрана научная деятельность профессорско-преподавательского состава Термезского государственного университета и их участие в международных публикациях за 2019–2025 гг. На основе анализа временных рядов разработаны экспоненциальная и полиномиальная модели тренда для прогнозирования темпов роста научных публикаций. Полученные результаты позволили оценить и проанализировать параметры моделей, а также сформулировать соответствующие научные выводы.

Ключевые слова: метод наименьших квадратов, международная научная база данных Scopus, модель экспоненциального тренда, линейная регрессия, регрессионная модель, точность модели, прогнозное значение, среднеквадратическая ошибка.

INTRODUCTION

In determining the rankings of higher education institutions (HEIs), scientific articles indexed in the Scopus international database and their corresponding citation indicators are considered among the most significant evaluation criteria. These indicators reflect the academic potential of higher education institutions and their level of international recognition. Data obtained from the Scopus database are commonly assessed across the following dimensions when evaluating the ranking performance of higher education institutions:

- **Number of publications** – the total number of articles published by university faculty members and researchers in journals indexed in the Scopus database during recent years (typically within the last five-year period).

- **Citation indicators (h-index)** – the frequency with which Scopus-indexed publications authored by HEI researchers are cited in the international scientific community. This indicator reflects the scientific influence and global visibility of research outputs.

- **International collaboration** – scientific publications indexed in Scopus and co-authored with international researchers contribute positively to ranking performance and serve as an important indicator of global academic cooperation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical foundations of modeling higher education institution (HEI) rankings have been extensively developed by international scholars. In particular, Henk F. Moed, in his seminal work *Citation Analysis in Research Evaluation*, scientifically substantiates that the analysis of scientific publications and citation indicators constitutes one of the most objective tools for assessing the academic potential of higher education institutions. The scholar emphasizes that the study of publication dynamics should focus not only on the number of scientific articles but also on the contextual significance and impact of citations. This approach highlights the importance of considering both qualitative and quantitative indicators when modeling institutional rankings.

Furthermore, the h-index proposed by Jorge E. Hirsch has had a substantial impact on the assessment of scientific productivity. Hirsch demonstrates the importance of maintaining a balance between the number of publications (quantity) and citation impact (quality) when evaluating academic performance. This methodology is widely applied as a benchmark for forecasting the academic potential of universities and modeling their positions in international rankings.

In his research, Ismael Rafols interprets the growth of scientific publications not merely as an increase in statistical indicators but as an expansion of the scientific knowledge network. Rafols' approaches are particularly valuable for explaining qualitative transformations that occur over time when modeling publication dynamics within higher education institutions.

In Uzbekistan, the scientific views of B. Begalov are of considerable importance in the statistical modeling of economic and social processes. In his studies, the scholar emphasizes the significance of econometric methods, including regression analysis, for evaluating changes in economic indicators over time. In particular, his approaches to time-series smoothing and trend model construction provide a methodological basis for forecasting indicators with complex dynamics, such as the growth of scientific publications in higher education institutions.

Scientific studies conducted by G. Abduxamidov on the economic mechanisms of higher education development reveal comprehensive approaches to assessing the performance of educational institutions. His research highlights that both the quantity and quality of international publications serve as important criteria in the formation of higher education rankings. In addition, the scholar examines economic and organizational strategies aimed at effectively managing these indicators and strengthening the international competitiveness of higher education institutions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The data presented below constitute a time series reflecting the growth dynamics of scientific articles published by the faculty members of Termiz State University in the Scopus international scientific database during 2019–2025 (Table 1).

Table 1
Information on the Number of Scopus-Indexed Articles Published by the Faculty of Termiz State University¹

№	Year	Number of Articles
1	2019	9
2	2020	27
3	2021	27
4	2022	42
5	2023	89
6	2024	179
7	2025	253

The presented data demonstrate a pronounced upward trend in the number of scientific publications over the study period. Given the accelerated nature of this growth, the exponential trend model is considered the most

1 Source: Developed by the Author

appropriate forecasting tool, as the observed increase follows a progressive rather than a linear pattern. The application of an exponential model enables a more accurate representation of the dynamics of publication activity and provides a reliable basis for forecasting future trends in scientific output (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Growth dynamics of Scopus-indexed articles by Termiz State University faculty (2019–2025)²

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

When analyzing the presented data, it can be observed that the indicators increase substantially from year to year (for example, from 179 in 2024 to 253 in 2025). To describe this process more accurately, an exponential trend equation is applied:

$$Y_t = a \cdot e^{bt} \quad (1)$$

where:

- \hat{y} is the forecasted value of the indicator;
- t is the time variable (year sequence: 2019 = 1, 2020 = 2, ..., 2025 = 7);
- a is the initial value coefficient;
- b is the growth-rate coefficient.

According to the data presented in Table 1, a temporary stabilization was observed in 2021 (27 to 27), whereas a substantial increase occurred during 2023–2025. The data series (9, 27, 27, 42, 89, 179, 253) demonstrates a non-linear and accelerating growth pattern over time. The mathematical representation of this process is expressed as follows:

$$\ln(Y_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot t \quad (2)$$

In this equation, e^b is equivalent to the annual growth factor. Thus, $e^b = 1.535$, where b represents the growth-rate coefficient. This indicates an average annual growth rate of approximately 54%.

Furthermore,

$$\ln(Y_t) = 1.8216 + 0.54t \quad (3)$$

Using this equation, forecast values can be calculated for each subsequent year.

At present, these calculations can be performed efficiently using statistical software packages, which generate the required estimates within seconds.

The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.966$) reflects the overall explanatory power of the model. The obtained result indicates that 96.6% of the variation in the number of Scopus-indexed articles can be explained by the time factor (t). This demonstrates a very high level of model reliability and explanatory capacity.

The overall significance of the model is assessed through the F-test. Since the R^2 value is high (approximately 0.95 or above), the F-statistic is correspondingly large, confirming the statistical significance and effectiveness of

2 Source: Developed by the Author

the model as a whole.

The growth-rate coefficient (b) indicates that the number of Scopus-indexed articles increases annually by approximately 53.5% on a logarithmic scale ($e^b = 1.535$, corresponding to approximately 53.5% growth). The t-statistic (11.93) is also considerably high, indicating that the influence of the time factor is statistically significant and highly reliable (Figure 2).

The model was additionally evaluated using Gretl statistical software.

Figure 2. Analysis of Model (5) values in the Gretl software³

Based on the exact coefficients obtained through Microsoft Excel, the recalculated forecast for the period 2026–2030 is presented below.

$$y_t = a \cdot b^t \quad (4)$$

In this equation, t denotes the time sequence (where t = 8 for 2026, t = 9 for 2027, and so forth) (Table 2).

Table 2
Five-year forecast results⁴

№	Year	Forecast Value
1	2026	447
2	2027	766
3	2028	1312
4	2029	2248
5	2030	3851

The forecast results can also be illustrated graphically (Figure 3).

3 Source: Developed by the Author
4 Source: Developed by the Author

Figure 3. Forecast Values for 2026–2030 Based on the Growth Dynamics of Scopus-Indexed Articles Published by Faculty Members of Termiz State University During 2019–2025⁵

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conducted research confirmed the scientific and practical effectiveness of econometric modeling in assessing scholarly publication activity within higher education institutions. The analyses carried out using Termiz State University as a case study demonstrate that the growth dynamics of the university's scientific potential are not linear but exhibit a progressive exponential pattern. This trend reflects the cumulative nature of academic activity and highlights the important role of previous publications in establishing a foundation for high-quality research and expanding international scientific collaboration.

The selected exponential trend model demonstrates a high level of statistical reliability and serves as an effective tool for forecasting scientific performance indicators and evaluating the influence of the time factor on research activity. The findings provide a valuable analytical basis for developing research strategies in higher education institutions, improving the allocation of academic resources, and enhancing mechanisms that encourage faculty participation in international publication activities.

Logical direction for future research involves integrating the proposed model into multifactor analytical systems that incorporate not only quantitative publication growth but also qualitative indicators, including citation metrics and research impact measures. Such an approach would expand the practical applicability of the methodology and contribute to more effective management of the scientific potential of higher education institutions.

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